

Using Haptic Feedback in Digital Rectal Examination Training

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Abstract. Prostate cancer is one of the most common cancer globally, particularly among men aged over 50. Digital rectal examination (DRE) is one of the first-line method for diagnosing and screening for the prostate cancer. However, medical students often lack sufficient training in performing DRE effectively. In this regard, we are developing a digital tool that seamlessly integrates digital simulation with haptic feedback to transform DRE training. Our method relies on the Finite Element Method (FEM) to create a detailed model of the probing-finger, organs, and their interactions. The contact forces generated by the probing-finger's movements in simulation, are then fed back to the user via a haptic device. We aim to accurately replicate mechanical properties associated with prostate in different conditions and provide realistic feedback, facilitating the preparation of medical professionals for DRE procedures. This approach has the potential to improve the effectiveness and accessibility of DRE training, ultimately contributing to better patient care and outcomes in prostate cancer diagnosis and management.

Keywords: Medical Simulation · Digital Rectal Exam · Augmented Reality

1 Introduction and Related Work

Digital rectal examination (DRE) is a common screening technique for prostate cancer. It involves the insertion of a lubricated, gloved finger into the rectum and feels the prostate through the rectal wall for lumps or abnormal areas [2]. Research have shown, combined with prostate-specific antigen (PSA) testing, up to a 30% detection rate of prostate cancer when suspicious DRE findings are reported [4]. Despite the established clinical utility, studies have revealed a concerning gap in the preparedness of final-year medical students to perform this procedure effectively. Various methods have been employed to train clinicians in DRE, [7]. However, the traditional approaches are often proven costly and may induce discomfort or stress for both students and patients, particularly for the examination in the pelvic area like DRE[8]. Moreover, the availability of training scenarios is limited, with existing training manikins offering only a handful of scenarios at a considerable cost. For instance, the training manikin on the market [1] cost more than £ 2000 and only have six different training scenarios.

Augmented reality (AR) presents a promising solution for medical training. By using AR, trainees can experience a wide range of situations at a lower cost and receive immersive, real-time feedback, better preparing them for performing procedures on real patients. In [6], the authors propose an augmented reality (AR) tool to facilitate

learning of internal techniques for digital rectal examination (DRE). The emphasis is on the positioning of the finger in the anus. While the developed tool provides valuable virtual visualization of the examining finger and internal organs, aiding learners in mastering finger alignment during DRE procedures, it faces limitations. Firstly, the tool is restricted by the number of scenarios possible with the mannequin. Secondly, its effectiveness relies heavily on the calibration accuracy of the HoloLens, which can be around a centimeter – a significant margin considering the average prostate size.

To address these limitations, we propose a novel approach utilizing FEM-based simulations for detailed mechanical modeling of various scene elements and AR-based haptic device to render diverse training scenario. The mechanical models can capture the interaction forces between organs and examining virtual finger, while also incorporating the texture variations resulting from disease progression. The calculated forces will be relayed to a haptic device to provide realistic force feedback to the user. We plan to leverage a haptic system similar to the one developed by Zhakypov et al. [9]. This origami-designed device made of flexible resin provides adjustable tactile feedback, four degrees of motion, force output for interaction, and sweatability. The combination of the FEM-based simulation and AR-based haptic feedback device will enable trainees to learn the different stages of prostate disease progression at lower cost.

2 System

Our system will include a numeric module to simulate organ and probing finger interactions, and a haptic device to provide user force feedback.

Fig. 1. Simulation of the probing finger touch the prostate, rendered using Blender.

The numerical simulation used Simulation Open Framework Architecture (SOFA). It will model the interactions between the probing finger, rectum, and prostate. Data from the Cross-institution Male Pelvic Structures dataset [5] is used to generate anatomically accurate models of the rectum and the prostate. The finger movement is simulated based on cable actuation, modeled using Cosserat theory [3]. To achieve realistic interactions between the finger and organs, as well as between organs themselves, we employ a constraint-based method [3]. Figure 1 shows a scene with DRE setup.

Fig. 2. System diagram of the proposed DRE training system.

The primary objective of our system is to simulate the prostate under various conditions, including benign prostatic hyperplasia and carcinoma. Benign prostatic hyperplasia involves increased prostate volume, while carcinomas involve uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells. The simulation will take the changes into account and determine interaction forces. The haptic interface uses a custom device that moves an actuated silicone under the fingertip to provide tactile sensation. The silicone's pneumatic actuation depends on the simulation scenario. For example, in a carcinoma simulation, the silicone cavity is emptied to highlight granularity, providing the user with a grainy feeling. Figure 2 shows a diagram of the proposed training system. After the first version of the setup, we will conduct experiments with our colleagues at ONCOLille (<https://www.oncolille.eu/>) to validate our simulation results.

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References

1. Male rectal examination trainer - advanced (light skin tone) — limbsandthings.com, <https://limbsandthings.com/uk/products/60171>
2. Prostate cancer screening — cancer.gov, <https://www.cancer.gov/types/prostate/patient/prostate-screening-pdq>
3. Adagolodjo, Y., Renda, F., Duriez, C.: Coupling numerical deformable models in global and reduced coordinates for the simulation of the direct and the inverse kinematics of soft robots. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* **6**(2), 3910–3917 (2021)
4. Carvalhal, G.F., Smith, D.S., Mager, D.E., Ramos, C., Catalona, W.J.: digital rectal examination for detecting prostate cancer at prostate specific antigen levels of 4 ng./ml. or less **161**(3), 835–839
5. Li, Y., Fu, Y., Gayo, I.J.M.B., Yang, Q., Min, Z., Saeed, S.U., Yan, W., Wang, Y., Noble, J.A., Emberton, M., Clarkson, M.J., Huisman, H., Barratt, D.C., Prisacariu, V.A., Hu, Y.: Prototypical few-shot segmentation for cross-institution male pelvic structures with spatial registration **90**, 102935
6. Muangpoon, T., Haghighi Osgouei, R., Escobar-Castillejos, D., Kontovounisios, C., Bello, F.: Augmented reality system for digital rectal examination training and assessment: System validation. **22**(8), e18637, place: Canada
7. Nikendei, C., Diefenbacher, K., Köhl-Hackert, N., Lauber, H., Huber, J., Herrmann-Werner, A., Herzog, W., Schultz, J.H., Jünger, J., Krautter, M.: Digital rectal examination skills: first training experiences, the motives and attitudes of standardized patients **15**(1), 7
8. Theroux, R., Pearce, C.: Graduate students' experiences with standardized patients as adjuncts for teaching pelvic examinations. **18**(9), 429–435, place: United States
9. Zhakypov, Z., Okamura, A.M.: FingerPrint: A 3-d printed soft monolithic 4-degree-of-freedom fingertip haptic device with embedded actuation. In: 2022 IEEE 5th International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft). pp. 938–944